

The Causal Presently¹

Michael Zammit

Mahārāja Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī (1913–97)² was *Śaṅkarācārya* of the *Jyotir Math* monastery, an instituted proponent of *Śaṅkara's Advaita Vedānta* from 1953 to 1980. He was a direct disciple of *Brahmananda Sarasvatī* (1871–1953) also known as *Guru Dev* and succeeded him as *Śaṅkarācārya* for modern time. In a most reassuring message about spirituality from 20 October 1989, *Mahārāja Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī* said:

Whosoever enquires will be provided for. Even if there are no more questions, satisfaction will be there because spiritual knowledge will never abandon anyone in the dark and will bring enlightenment and full realisation. That is its assured potentiality. Blessings and good wishes for the work.³

This quote suggests that spirituality originates from a fundamental, direct and ever present experience. From this deep, often personal encounter with the divine, the transcendent, or ultimate reality, different *schools of spirituality* emerge. Like *Śāntānanda Sarasvatī*, Kees Waaijman (1942–2023) in his 2002 book, *Spirituality: Forms, Foundations, Methods* emphasises that spirituality is rooted in experience rather than just in religious systems. Schools of spirituality are built upon such foundational spiritual encounters. In short, spirituality starts with a deep (often individual) experience (sometimes referred to as the

1 Dedicated to a dear friend and fellow seeker of *pregnant silence*, William Driscoll.

2 Except for *Mahārāja Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī* and some other similar names, all Sanskrit terms will be transcribed into the nearest English language phonetic equivalents for the sake of simplicity.

3 *Mahārāja Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, Conversations with Mahārāja Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī*, 5 vols. (London: The School of Economic Science, 2017–19), 4:115.

Source-Experience), from which various spiritual traditions and teachings then emerge. This book, one of the most authoritative texts in the academic study of spirituality, treats the encounter with the sacred as heuristic, investigative rather than dogmatic, emphasising its dynamic and transformative nature.

Waaajman therefore defines spirituality as the divine-human relational process that transforms a person through a deep encounter with the sacred (the *Source-Experience*). This experience precedes formal doctrines and traditions – meaning that structured religious and spiritual schools emerge as interpretations and expressions of this fundamental encounter. Already both William James (1842–1910) in his *The Varieties of Religious Experience*, and Rudolf Otto (1869–1937) in *The Idea of the Holy*, speak of this.

William James emphasises religious experience as the foundation of spirituality, describing mystical encounters as immediate, direct, and ineffable experiences of the divine. Rudolf Otto speaks in Kantian terms, of the *numinous experience*, where one perceives the divine as *mysterium tremendum et fascinans*, both awe-inspiring and deeply attractive.

Pierre Hadot (1922–2010) in turn, in his last text, *Don't Forget to Live*, challenges and defies the entrenched prejudicial narratives that declare what it is to be a philosopher.

(The philosophers') obsession to trace the boundaries of their discipline and enforce them against any unwanted intrusion... institutional affiliation... [becomes] systematically used as a distinctive mark of belonging: if you do not work in a university philosophy department, you surely aren't a real philosopher!⁴

The dogmatic aspect of such practices and rigid opinions is certainly problematic. In this regard in his 1992 Pulitzer Prize philosophical novel called *Lila*, Robert M. Pirsig (1928–2017) draws the distinction between philosophy and what University departments, according to his view, generally practice, *i.e.*, philosophology. In his terms philosophology is to philosophy as musicology is to music.⁵ In his view the academic, the 'philosophologist' is not necessarily a practitioner of philosophy.

4 P. Hadot, *Don't Forget to Live* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2023), x.

5 R. M. Pirsig, *Lila: An Inquiry into Morals*, rev. ed. 2006 (New York: Bantam Books, 1991), 349ff.

To define something is to subordinate it to a tangle of intellectual relationships. And when you do that you destroy real understanding.⁶

This suggests that Pirsig values direct, original and experiential engagement with philosophical concepts over the mere academic, fusty and actually boring reading of existing ideas. He discusses the limitations of merely defining concepts and the potential loss of genuine understanding that results from over-intellectualization. For example, he mentions indeed, that *mystics*,⁷ and *poets* (the real philosophers) argue that thinking is not a path to reality and that attempting to just define, describe something often destroys and subdues the opportunity of understanding it deeply.

Hadot who also thinks of these so-called *mystics*, the initiated into the mysteries of an authentically experienced and truly lived knowledge as the genuine philosophers, then seeks to redefine and realign, re-orient the philosophical process, presenting it not as a set of doctrines and theories, but as a practice that he boldly calls *spiritual*, an exercise of self-transformation, involving a way of life.⁸

The professors of philosophy operating with their finely educated, preformed, rigid, and fixed ideas of who counts as a philosopher and who does not, will necessarily be led like lambs to the slaughter of their wisdom severely *limiting their chances to read, absorb and experience a variety of ancient and modern texts as occasions to practice philosophy as an exercise of self-transformation, at one and the same time intellectual and ethical.*⁹

Genuine philosophical discourse should in the final analysis be in the service of philosophical life insofar as it may contribute to the transformation of ourselves and our lives allowing for a radical rethinking of the stale, fetid idea of philosophy as dogmatically sanctioned institutionally by university departments. Naming it and arguing for or against ‘transcendence,’ ‘authenticity’ or whatever, actually does next to nothing. Śāntānanda Sarasvatī mentions how difficult this process of self-transformation is:

6 Ibid., 68.

7 From Greek *mustēs*, the initiated person.

8 P. Hadot, *Philosophy as a Way of Life: Spiritual Exercises from Socrates to Foucault* (New York: Wiley, 1995), 264ff.

9 Hadot 2023, xi.

This is the nature of the individual from which he operates. This is his limit. He cannot transcend it until he transforms it. To transform prakriti (nature) is to make it reasonable and with rational prakriti one could transcend it. Only through viveka (enlightenment) may one transcend this...¹⁰

A contemporary causal, spiritual proposal in this regard, that dares defy and confront the deadlock, is lifted by Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī from the ancient Sanskrit Upanishadic texts, and specifically from the *Muṇḍaka* Upanishad that confidently declares ‘*Satyam eva jayate*,’ lit. Truth alone triumphs.¹¹

In *Advaita Vedānta* this phrase is primarily interpreted in a metaphysical, causal, spiritual context. The ultimate victory of truth is highlighted as the realisation of *Brahman*, the non-dual reality, the Absolute.¹² Mundane truth or untruth are transcended, and the focus turns on spiritual awakening (*viveka*) that bares the illusory nature of the world (*prakriti*) to realise the eternal, unchanging nature of the Self of all (*Paramātman*)¹³ as identical with *Brahman*. The “triumph” of spiritual awakening is the factual liberation of the individual from ignorance enabling the attainment of ultimate unity.

Prakriti, literally ‘making or placing before or at first,’ signifies the original and natural form of any creaturely condition. The term denotes primary substance and represents the dynamic energy and the manifestation of nature. For man *prakriti* is his innate human nature, his essential humanity.¹⁴

Avidyā,¹⁵ ignorance (lower, in the sense of mundane knowledge) is the root cause of the mistaken identification of the Self with the body, mind, and the ego (called *ahankāra*, lit. ‘I, the doer’). Realisation involves the removal of *avidya* through self-inquiry (*ātmā-vichāra*) meditation (*dhyāna*) discernment (*viveka*) and renunciation (*vairāga*) the practice of detachment from worldly

10 Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 1:260.

11 Eight *Upaniṣads*, trans. Swāmi Gambhīrānanda. 2 vols. (Calcutta: Advaita Ashrama, 1982), 2:152.

12 *Brahman* (ब्रह्मन्) – The Ultimate Reality: “*The individual self (jīva) and Brahman are not different. realising this is the goal of spiritual knowledge.*” Quoted in Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 3:116

13 *Ātmā* (आत्मा) – The Self: “*The Self (Ātmā) is the only reality, and once it is known, everything else is known.*” 2:101

14 See Monier-Williams, *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, 653ff.

15 *Vidyā* (विद्या) – Higher Knowledge: “*Two kinds of knowledge exist: aparā vidyā (lower knowledge) and parā vidyā (higher, spiritual knowledge). True wisdom is parā vidyā, the knowledge of the Self.*” Quoted in Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 2:57.

desires and ego-based attachments to reveal the Self's true status as existence (*sat*), pure, limitless consciousness (*chit*), and bliss (*ānanda*).¹⁶

In *ātmā-vichāra*, asking the iconic question “*Who am I?*” means to peel away layers of false identification with the body, mind and the ego claiming the consequences of actions. *Dhyāna*, in turn is the practice of meditation and contemplation accessing clarity and tranquillity (*sattva*)¹⁷ by focusing the mind on the unity of existence and the Upanishadic teachings of the *Advaita*, non-dual philosophy.

Viveka, ‘discrimination,’ and ‘distinction,’ in the non-dual, *Advaita Vedānta* philosophy of *Śāntānanda Sarasvatī*, is ‘discernment,’ the power of separating the invisible unmanifest causal from the visible phenomenal world (or spirit from matter, truth from untruth, reality from mere semblance or illusion). It is a method to distinguish and discriminate the real (*sat*, ‘what is’) from the unreal (*asat* ‘what is not’)¹⁸

In the *Advaita Vedānta* context and as it is understood presently, self-realisation (*ātmajñāna*) refers to an experiential and direct appreciation of the ultimate truth, which is the non-dual nature of reality, the truth that the individual self (*jīva*) is identical with absolute reality (*Brahman*). This realisation is no mere intellectual knowledge or some theoretical understanding of a concept but a profound inner awakening that fundamentally transforms one’s perception of both the self and existence. Therefore, besides overcoming ignorance, realisation, for *Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī* also involves what is known as *aparoksha anubhūti*, perceptible, direct, and unmediated knowledge.

Realisation is direct, immediate, and beyond the scope of the senses or the intellect. It is described as *aparoksha anubhūti* (non-mediated experience), where the seeker *knows* through direct insight that their true self is none other than *Brahman*. This is not gained through reasoning or scriptural study alone (*paroksha jñāna*,¹⁹ which is ‘indirect knowledge’), but through deep meditation and self-inquiry, often under guidance.

16 See Monier-Williams, *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, 108.

17 *Sattva* (सत्त्व) – Purity and Clarity in Spiritual Practice: “*The mind must be brought to a sattvic state before true knowledge can dawn.*” Quoted in *Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, Conversations*, 1:84

18 See Monier-Williams, *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, 987.

19 *Jñāna* (ज्ञान) – Spiritual Knowledge or True Wisdom: “*Jñāna is not about collecting information but about removing ignorance. It is the direct experience of the Self.*” Quoted in *Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, Conversations*, 3:142.

In the light of all this information, Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī warns the stale philosopher whose knowing has grown alien to her being, that:

When realisation of the Self is not universal but confined, then it would be the misguided voice of *ahankāra* (lit. ‘the claiming self’) and immaturity could lead one away from *sadhana*, the discipline of the spiritual way. One may presume to have realised the wisdom, but it may not be real. It becomes an obstacle to further progress. Just as a loose connection in electricity can spark a brilliant light in a flash but it can never remain constant.

A flash of true knowledge can take place, but usually it is held by *ahankāra*, and it turns into ignorance, a memory of a past event which cannot be alive and constant. The purity of *ahankāra* is very necessary, otherwise the light of knowledge, being confined, would lose its purity and brilliance... This is the difference between *paroksha* (lit. ‘indirect,’ ‘mediated’) and *aparoksha* (lit. ‘direct,’ ‘immediate’) knowledge.²⁰

The essential unity of all existence is captured in the *Advaita* core teaching, *Tat Tvam Asi*²¹ (lit. ‘that thou art’) which implies the dissolution of the apparent duality between the individual self, the *jīva* and the universal self, the *Brahman*. The seeker understands that the distinction between subject and object, self and other, and even existence and non-existence is illusory, *mithyā*. The basic concept of pure *Advaita* is enshrined in one of the sayings of Śrī *Adi Śaṅkarācārya*.²²

brahma satyañ jaganmithyā jīvo brahmaiva nāparaḥ

‘The *Brahman* exists; the world is illusion; there is no difference between the *jīva* and the *Brahman*.’

Śāntānanda Sarasvatī continues and he explains this. He says:

20 Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 4:68.

21 The mahāvākya “tat tvam asi” (तत् त्वम् असि), meaning “That Thou Art” or “You are That,” appears in Chāndogya *Upaniṣad* 6.8.7.

22 Modern scholarship places him, the original *Śaṅkara*, in the earlier part of the 8th-century CE (c.700–750)

When it is simply said that the *Brahman* exists, it means that the *Brahman* exists without the help of anyone. This makes It the independent element in the creation. It exists by itself, and, because It is not dependent on anyone else, It is eternal and all-powerful.

The world is said to be an illusion, which does not mean that it does not exist. It has existence as in time and space, but it has no independent existence. Its existence depends on the *Brahman* and, because it is dependent, it is not absolute and cannot exist all the time. It comes into being and gets dissolved; and its coming into being and subsequent dissolution depend on *Brahman*. This is why the world is said to be an illusion.... [T]he *Brahman* is like the ocean on which *jīvas* emerge and merge like waves of different magnitudes and duration; and this will go on without end.

But a man of understanding sees the ocean for the waves and realises the advaita of *jīva* and *Brahman*.²³

The triumph of truth (*satyam eva jayate*) is understood as the realisation that *Brahman* alone is real (*satyam*), while the phenomenal world (*jagat*) is illusory (*mithyā*). This realisation occurs when one transcends causal ignorance (*avidyā*) and experiences the non-dual nature of reality. The human experience of duality, the separation between subject and object, self and the other, arises from ignorance dispelled only by the knowledge of *Brahman* as *Ātman*. This triumph is not external or worldly but internal, extremely subtle, and spiritual. It is the victory of *ātmajñāna*, self-realisation where the individual's assurance of her identity as *That (tat)* is as securely embedded in her being as is her conviction that she is human. This begs the question therefore as to where or from what does humanity manifest.

The investigation then turns to questing after the essentials, the bases for being human. What am I, perhaps even prior to being human?

Though primarily metaphysical, this question also holds an ethical dimension in *Advaita*. Truthfulness (*satyam*) in thought, speech, and action is considered a prerequisite for the seeker of non-dual spiritual progress. Living in accordance with truth helps deconstruct the mind into discovering its genuinely limitless nature, making the individual receptive to the realisation of *Advaita*. But again, a firm word of caution is necessary!

23 Sāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 3:28.

In the search for transformation and Self-realisation, plenty of knowledge (is) made available. When people submit themselves to discipline their sincere approach and continuous effort with the help of true knowledge must bring about some transformation on the way. Spiritual knowledge on the way to Self-realisation will manifest as power, as power of knowledge, efficiency, and dynamism. Power can easily turn into pride although its purer manifestation is humility and renunciation. Although the rise of *ahankāra* (ego) as pride does not necessarily follow from higher levels of power, it is possible because it is seen to happen again and again in the spiritual realm, apart from worldly affairs and positions. People, having acquired a higher level, take a little turn and fill their mind with pride at the wonderful knowledge, efficiency, and dynamism which they have brought under their control. They do not necessarily depart from the spiritual way, but it does unnecessarily hinder their chances for further transformation.

Like *Ātman*, consciousness is not an individual, but *ahankāra* (the egotism) of being the master of knowledge does mean an individual who will have to remain outside the transcended realm of the universal. Rise of the level of consciousness means universalisation of the individual which is made easy through humility and renunciation and made difficult by pride. Pride makes one cold and rigid. Pride and ego belong to the realm of *hitā* (the acquired, the imposed, and the set up). Therefore, those who have had the good fortune to have been given access to the true knowledge to transcend and realise the *Ātman* as advaita do need a sound of caution that care must be taken.²⁴

In *Bhagavad Gītā* (vi.35), the conversation between Krishna and Arjuna, Krishna concedes that:

Undoubtedly, O mighty-armed one, the mind is difficult to control and restless; but through practice, O son of Kunti, and detachment, it can be grasped, it can be controlled.

*Asaṁśayaṁ mahābāho...mano durnigrahaṁ calam...abhyāsenā tu kaunteya...vairāgyeṇa ca gr̥hyate.*²⁵

24 Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 4:108ff.

25 Vyasa: 1981, 201.

Vairagya,²⁶ Renunciation and detachment are therefore, an efficient antidote to pride.

In the world man is confronted with material and mental worlds. He finds himself very small in comparison with the universe. His capacity is little, and his energy is meagre. He cannot comprehend the universe fully, and whatever he does comprehend, he cannot control or command.

Naturally he wants to join in. He seeks someone greater to help him and this search has landed him with the concept of the Absolute who is most powerful and most merciful.

The Absolute is said to have all *aiśvarya* (glory of wealth), *vīrya* (power of potentiality), *yaśas* (acclamation and fame), *śrī* (goodness and service), *jñāna* (knowledge), *vairāgya* (power of detachment) and this makes him the greatest of all to look towards. This gives him the creative (*sattva*), sustaining (*rajas*) and regulating (*tamas*) power over all the beings of the universe.²⁷

This is so attractive to being human and suggests that the first step to *abhyāsa*, practice, is *bhāvanā*,²⁸ the spiritual feeling that arises as a consequence of giving very fine attention to anything; in other words, devotion, reflection leading to contemplation which involves carefully cultivating the stability of non-dual awareness.

The man of devotion, as others, keeps on changing, for the changing gunas [the qualities of stillness, activity, and inertia]²⁹ exercise their claim over him. Thus, he must go to sleep, must get up and must get into action just to live and do his devotional work.

[But] there is a golden rule behind this. The laws of the universe bind man in every aspect of his existence except in one aspect. The individual is free in *bhāvanā*. This should be taken as dedication.

26 *Vairagya* from the seminal *ranj*, in the realm of *rāgā*, colouring; is the freedom from all worldly desires, the power of detachment. See Monier-Williams, *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, 1025/2.

27 Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 2:136ff.

28 *Bhāvanā* from the seminal *bhū*, 'becoming' in the realm of 'being' or 'is-ness'(as); is the spiritual feeling of devotion, faith in; reflection, and contemplation. Monier-Williams, *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, 755/1.

29 *Sattva, Rajas, and Tamas*.

An individual can dedicate any *bhāvanā* to anyone, (or to anything). He can deliberately create a *bhāvanā* within himself and work accordingly. Even in miserable conditions, people become happy or in happy conditions become miserable because they choose it like that.³⁰

In an interesting shift Śāntānanda Sarasvatī links this to the ancient Sanskrit language. *Sanskrit*, he says, *is the one language which alone is capable of (expressing and) working for both worldly communications and spiritual, higher knowledge.*³¹ Its refinements and truly natural conditions contain original laws and make use of original sounds and their combinations. This ensures that through the proper study and use of Sanskrit, spiritual, causal truths emerge. *Apart from this*, he concludes, *the language of bhāvanāh, the emotions, is the medium of higher knowledge, or spiritual knowledge.*³²

The term *Samskrita* means “refined,” “polished,” or “perfected.”³³ It likely came into formal use to distinguish the standardized, grammatically codified form of the language (especially post-*Pāṇini*, around the 4th-century BCE) from *Prākṛits*, the more natural and vernacular dialects used in the daily mundane *bhāshā*, speech. *Samskrita*, the language created from the originally practiced speech forms was perfected into what came to be called *Āryā Vāk* or *Āryā Bhāshā*, the language of the *Āryas*, the seekers of excellence. In other contexts, especially the later post-Vedic ones, but still in the early periods, the language was associated with the Brahmins and sometimes referred to in that way as *Brahmī Bhāshā*, the Brahmanic language emphasising its sacred and liturgical use. In the earliest Vedic texts, especially in the *Rigveda*, the language is often referred to simply as *Vāk*, meaning sacred or divine speech. The personification of speech in this context is the goddess *Vāk* who appears in the *Vedas*. This term referred to in the metrical language of the *Vedas* as *Chandas* was used to describe the specific poetic form and language of the Vedic hymns, particularly the *Rigveda*. *Chandas* is also one of the six *Vedāngas* (the auxiliary disciplines of the *Vedas*), dealing with Vedic meter. Thus, prior to being called *Samskrita Bhāshā*, the language didn’t have one fixed name but was identified by function (as sacred speech), by form (as metrical speech), or indeed by cultural association (as the language of the noble).

30 Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, *Conversations*, 2:133.

31 *Ibid.*, 2:58.

32 *Ibid.*

33 See Monier-Williams, *Sanskrit-English Dictionary*, 1120/3.

Pāṇini's Sanskrit meditations (his renown *Ashtādhyāyī*) besides being informative about the language also actually provide and help structure how relations in the world are formed and understood. For instance, case distinctions are grammatically clear, but from the *Advaita* and the *bhāvanā* perspectives, they reinforce duality and indeed multiplicity: a subject acting upon an object using instruments in a place and a time according to some intention. Case distinctions therefore are differential and as they describe, they correspondingly work in favour of the proliferation of creation.

Śāntānanda Sarasvatī would say that this view, though useful, is partial. We must train ourselves, through *bhāvanā*, through dedication, to comprehend all agents, objects, tools and locations as the *Paramātman*, the one Self of all. So while on the one hand grammar teaches us to distinguish and separate, on the other *bhāvanā* needs to educate and help cultivate for us the art of the recognition of unity and integrity. Indeed, the Sanskrit term used for 'grammar' is *vyākaraṇa*³⁴ which literally means 'deconstruction' besides 'separation,' 'distinction,' 'explanation' and 'detailed description.'

Advaita Vedānta accepts the Sanskrit language as an ideal pointer, and a best means to access truth. *Bharṭṛhari* (5th-century CE?) in his text on the philosophy of language, the *Vākyapadīya*, does not hesitate to boldly assert:

[Vyākaraṇa, deconstructive grammar is]... the door of freedom, the medicine for the diseases of language, the purifier of all sciences; it sheds its light on them;... it is the first rung on the ladder that leads up to the realisation of supernatural powers, and the straight royal road for those who seek freedom.³⁵

For *Śāntānanda Sarasvatī* the Sanskrit language, the thought embedded in it, and its deconstructive processes are the best supports for spiritual development, but certainly not final destinations.

In the deeper Vedic thought³⁶ as presented by *Śāntānanda Sarasvatī*, *Vāk*, speech manifests from four realms, four levels of expression:

34 Ibid., 1035/3.

35 Quoted in P. S. Filliozat, *The Sanskrit Language: An Overview*. (Varanasi: Indica Books, 2000), 65.

36 "There are four demarcated portions of speech. The Brahmins who control their mind know them. Three [quarters], being kept in a hidden place, do not have any movement. Humans speak the fourth [quarter] of speech." Rig Veda I.164.45. Quoted in Filliozat, *The Sanskrit Language*, 62.

1. *Parā Vāk* – the pure, limitless and undifferentiated root of speech.
2. *Pashyantī Vāk* – the intuitive, attitudinal visionary realm.
3. *Madhyamā Vāk* – the mental, conceptual speech.
4. *Vaikharī Vāk* – the spoken, articulated forms of speech on the tongue.

The Pāninian deconstructive process operates primarily in *Vaikharī Vāk* and in *Madhyamā Vāk*, whereas *Bhāvanā*, contemplation connects with *Pashyantī Vāk*, the causal realm where speech becomes visionary, a form of seeing, feeling truth rather than just uttering it.

So in practice speech arises from *parā*, the unbounded *nāda*, the silently pregnant roar of consciousness, and when seen and acknowledged at *pashyantī* and through *bhāvanā*, the attitudinal causal form of *madhyamā* is cast and conceptualized to be spoken and announced articulately at *vaikharī*, the tongue, in the realm of utterance.

The reverse process is the practice of renunciation, the ‘re-annunciation’ of the spoken, taking it back into its causal original form of silence.

You hear “*tat tvam asi*”³⁷ (the spoken annunciation as *vāk*), you think and conceptualize it (the mental formation of *vāk*), and reflecting thus you then see and visualise it through *bhāvanā* (at *pashyantī*) where a sincere and heart-felt dedication to truth can be made... to eventually, allow the merger with the ever-present original virile roar (*nāda*) of silence at *parā*. This is the transcendence of speech and of all its steadily deconstructed structures through living vision and practice, not logic.

While *Pāṇini’s Vyākaraṇa* (his deconstructive technique) shows how the world appears; *Śāntānanda’s bhāvanā* (his ‘re-annunciated’ dedication) shows how to see what it truly is.

Bhāvanā doesn’t reject grammar – it subsumes and transforms it. What begins as linguistic differentiation then, through disciplined vision and the deconstructive methods provided by *Pāṇini’s* genius, becomes the unified experience of *Brahman*.

In the *Advaita Vedānta* tradition, as taught by *Maharaja Śrī Śāntānanda Sarasvatī*, spirituality is not about beliefs but about a direct, unmediated

³⁷ *Lit. That Thou Art*; one of four great statements embedded in the Upanishadic literature designed to promote and spur the adept to the heightened consciousness of Self realisation.

realisation of non-duality. This aligns with Waaijman's concept of a *foundational Source-experience that gives rise to structured spiritual paths*. The teachings of Śāntānanda Sarasvatī, like those of the original Śrī Adi Śaṅkara, emphasise the direct experience of truth rather than trusting and relying solely on a cold and sterile pseudo-intellectual understanding.

Om paramātmāne namaḥ.

(*Om paramātmāne*, to the supreme Self of all, *namaḥ*, with reverence)

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